

Personality Traits as Correlates of Psychological Well-being and Suicidal Ideation in Adults

Twinkle¹, Gobind², Pinki³, Rakesh Behmani⁴

Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar, Haryana^{1,2,4}

Department of Psychology, Chaudhary Bansi Lal University, Bhiwani, Haryana³

There is a lot of evidence to support specific traits in personality that may enhance a person's vulnerability to suicide and connected to psychological well-being among twenty-somethings as grownups, individuals seem to be at a greater risk of having suicidal thoughts and acting on them. In this study, the researcher inspected the relationship of personality characteristics with suicide ideation and psychological well-being (n=200) of 20 to 30-year-old individuals, illustrative of the general population of Haryana. Subjects were measured using Big Five Inventory by Rammsted and John (2007). Adult Suicidal Ideation Questionnaire given by William (1987). Psychological Well-being Scale by Ryff (1995) Correlational analyses was applied to identify personality traits that correlate with suicide ideation and psychological well-being. Extravert and openness is positively correlated with psychological well being and negatively correlated with suicide ideation. likewise nueroticism is positively corelated with suicide ideation.

Keywords: personality traits, psychological well-being, suicide ideation, adults

Human existence can be explained in terms of many stages, with each developmental stage presenting its own unique set of opportunities, obstacles and challenges. One of the key events in a person's development is the transition to adulthood from adolescence. According to the American Psychological Association (2016), "adulthood is the stage of human development during which a person shows full physical development and maturity as well as experiences some biological, cognitive, social, personality, and other age-related changes. Adulthood, which begins following youth, is commonly split into three stages: Young adulthood (about ages 20 to 35), middle adulthood (roughly ages 36 to 64), and later adulthood (ages 65 & above)." Individuals encounter changes in social roles and normative expectations for their behaviour throughout this stage of life, as well as a degree of relative autonomy from their guardians. Throughout adulthood, the person experiences significant changes in their personality, mental health, and coping mechanisms.

Personality-trait change is greatest during early adulthood, between ages 18 and 40 (Roberts et al., 2006).

In a study conducted in the United States, Easterlin (2006) discovered that happiness tends to slightly increase from the age of 18 to midlife, and then gradually decrease afterward. This trend of age and happiness can be interpreted as having greater happiness in our early and later years of life, but happiness declines during middle age, most likely because of the numerous setbacks one encounters, including social, financial, and emotional pressure to deal with success or failure, the difficulty of adjusting to the role transition of becoming a responsible adult, maintaining social status, and the requirement to support family. Additionally, there is a correlation between age and suicidal ideation. The results of a study by Nock et al. (2008) demonstrate that suicidal ideation declines with age. However, suicide is more likely to occur among elderly people. After all, older people have a higher risk of suffering the death of a loved one, health problems, and functional impairment.

Author Note

¹Twinkle, Student, Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar, Haryana
E-mail: twinklenagar2001@gmail.com

²Gobind, Assitant Professor, Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology Hisar, Haryana
E-mail: gobindsinghy@gjust.org

³Pinki, Student, Msc Department of Psychology, Chaudhary Bansi Lal University, Bhiwani, Haryana
E-mail: pinkipsy2311@gmail.com

⁴Rakesh Behmani, Professors, Department of Applied Psychology Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar Haryana
E-mail: rakeshgjust@gmail.com

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Twinkle, Student, Department of Applied Psychology, Guru
E-mail: twinklenagar2001@gmail.com

Personality and Traits

The word 'Personality' is coined from the Latin word 'Persona', which was originally used to describe the mask used by theatre actors (Schultz, 2017). In psychology, personality has a much more broad meaning. Personality not only includes the behavioural aspects but also the way we think and behave. It includes everything about a person. Various psychologists have defined personality in different ways. But they all agree to the fact that personality helps us to determine behaviour of the person. As defined by Cattell (1950) "Personality is what permits us to predict what a person will do in a given situation." "Personality is the dynamic organization within the person of those psychophysical systems that characterize his/her characteristics adjustment to the environment" (Allport, 1961).

Five-factor model of personality: Five-factor model of personality was developed by Costa and McCrae (1987). These five factors (represented by the acronym OCEAN) are named as 'Big Five' by Goldberg (Oliver, 1990).

Openness to Experience (O): Those who score high on this dimension are rich in new experience, exploration. They are highly imaginative; entertain novel ideas and unconventional values. They appreciate art and are aesthetic sensitive. They are attentive and curious about both the inner and outer world.

Conscientiousness (C): Digman and Takemoto-Chock (1981) refer to this domain as 'will achieve' (Costa & McCrae, 1992). Those who score high on this factor are ambitious, hardworking, and self-disciplined. They have a purpose and a strong will to attain that. They are organised and strive for their achievement.

Extraversion (E): Extroverts are people who are fun-loving, sociable, and very talkative. They prefer parties, large groups, and social gatherings and are very energetic. Extroverts like and seek excitement in their lives.

Agreeableness (A): Those who are high on this factor are generous, trustworthy, helpful, and sympathetic to others. They are soft-hearted and forgive others easily. They like to help others so they get along with others easily. They even compromise for others and are socially preferred.

Neuroticism (N): High scorers on this indicator are more likely to experience unpleasant emotions that might be damaging, such as fear, rage, grief, and guilt. They are pessimistic and cope poorly with stress and anxiety. They are not able to control their impulses, get easily irritated and are very moody.

Studying psychological aspects of personality is considerably more than just a theoretical exercise. The results of personality studies can be used in a variety of fields, including business, economics, technology, medicine, and health. In order to find novel approaches to enhance both individual and societal health, we must first have a greater understanding of how personality functions.

Personality traits and Psychological well-being

Psychological well-being can be characterised as assessing the value of life and feeling content with our happiness and our lifestyles. In Psychology, Well-being is defined as the total of emotional well-being, social well-being and psychological well-being (Baumgardner & Crothers, 2014). Well-being, in Ryff's view, is more than happiness with life (Ryff, 1989). He developed a model of Well-being what he termed as "psychological well-being" defined as comprising six core dimensions includes (Ryff, 1995):

Self-acceptance: have a positive attitude toward ourselves, our strengths and weaknesses. Accepting our past, not criticising ourselves for our past mistakes instead growing out of them.

Positive Relationships with Others: have warm, trusting and empathetic relationships with others; are not showing off concern for others for their own sake or benefits; maintain close relationships with others.

Autonomy: are independent, self-reliant and have control of their thoughts, and actions within; act and evaluate themselves by their standards.

Environmental Mastery: have control over their environment and are not controlled by it; have the locus of control within; are capable to choose and create their environment.

Purpose in Life: have purpose and direction in their lives; holds the belief that life has meaning; live life one time a day.

Personal Growth: have a sense that they are growing into a mature person; are open to new experiences and to challenge their beliefs;

don't give up easily; and can change.

In middle adulthood, Katja et al. (2013) studied the relationship periodically between traits of personality and psychological well-being. Bivariate latent development curve analysis results show a strong correlation between a high level of PWB and low levels of neuroticism (.75) and extraversion (.55). Furthermore, there was a strong correlation between PWB and high levels of conscientiousness, openness, and agreeableness. Only openness was affected by the change factor, and openness increased from age 33 to age 50 in direct proportion to the beginning PWB level. When compared to emotional well-being, the connections between personality traits and PWB were considerably greater for neuroticism, extraversion, and openness., which was measured by overall life satisfaction.

Additionally, the relationship between The Big Five personality traits and psychological well-being was examined by Hicks and Mehta (2018). They found that PWB and agreeableness, extraversion, conscientiousness and openness to experience had positive relationships, while neuroticism and PWB had negative relationships. Age and gender are both linked significantly (in a negative way) with PWB and conscientiousness (.01) and positively (.05) with openness and neuroticism. Conscientiousness and Social Desirability both showed positive correlations with extraversion (.01) and conscientiousness, respectively. In conclusion, the findings reveal intriguing associations between age, gender, personality traits, and well-being indicators, highlighting the complex interplay of these factors in shaping individuals' psychological profiles.

On the basis of the review, it is found that personality has many traits or psychological characteristics. These traits directly relate with mental health, way of doing things, behaviour and psychological well-being of a person. Basically, traits are inborn as well as acquired, so environment and gene paly role in a healthy personality.

Personality Traits and Suicidal Ideation

Suicidal ideation is a medical term used for ideas or thoughts about killing oneself (Devi & Raju, 2018). People with suicidal ideation are preoccupied or wish to be dead. According to O'Carroll et al. (1996), "suicide ideation refers to self-reported thoughts of carrying out suicide-related behaviour". Suicidal behaviour-related thoughts and perceptions are included in suicidal ideation. A suicide attempt, to sum up, is a self-inflicted, self-destructive act carried out with some intention to die. Suicidal ideation is often fleeting and varies in degree. Some people believe that having suicidal thoughts is the first step toward actually committing suicide (Gili-Planas et al., 2001). Suicidal ideation can range from strong, deluded fixation to feeling that life is not worth living (Gili-Planas et al., 2001). It plays an important role in detecting and preventing suicide (Palmer, 2004).

Passive Suicide Ideation: when you have suicidal or self-destructive ideas such as "I wish I were dead" but no plan to carry it out and acted to kill yourself ((Liu et al., 2021).

Active Suicide Ideation: is when you have thoughts of suicide or self-harm and have developed a plan to carry it out and even acted out to kill you, Such as writing a death note and giving precocious things away to people (Liu et al., 2021).

Daniel et al. (2012) studied older adults' personalities and suicide ideation. Except for neuroticism, which had a medium-to-large

positive correlation with suicidal ideation, they found that personality traits showed negative relationships with suicidal ideation. In Chinese university students, Huang et al. (2019) investigated the association between disposition characteristics and the risk of suicidal ideation. 13.03 percent of the college students studied said they had considered suicide. Suicide ideation participants were more likely to be female, to be from rural areas, to have poor life quality, and to have psychological diseases than those who did not have suicide ideation. According to the study, extroversion has a protective impact against suicidal ideation while neuroticism, psychoticism, impulsivity, and violence are risk factors for suicidal ideation.

Although according to Lester and Voracek's (2013) research, there is no correlation between the occurrences of suicidal ideation and committed suicide in the United States and any state's Big Five personality trait scores. Suicidal ideation was inversely correlated with extraversion and mindfulness, and positively correlated with neuroticism. According to Tucker et al. (2014), suicidal ideation was favourably correlated with neuroticism and negatively correlated with extraversion and mindfulness. Hence when neuroticism increases, suicidal ideation also increases and vice versa, indicating a positive correlation. And when extraversion and mindfulness increase, suicidal ideation decreases and vice versa, indicating a negative correlation.

It concludes that the behaviour of a being is the product of thought, whether that behaviour is negative or positive, our personality characteristics play a major role in thinking. Personality traits play an important role in perceiving the environment. Perception and attitude towards the environment and bad experiences of life, generate suicidal thoughts.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the relationship between personality traits and psychological well-being among adults in Haryana
- To study the relationship between personality traits and suicide ideation among adults in Haryana

Hypotheses of the Study

- There will be no relationship between personality traits and psychological well-being among adults
- There will be no relationship between personality traits and suicide ideation among adults

Method

Participants

The sample of 200 was collected from different districts of Haryana. Out of the total sample, 100 were female and 100 were male. The age of the subjects ranged between 20-30 years. The sample has been collected from both rural and urban areas with different modes (both online & manually) so the sample is sufficiently heterogeneous to permit a generality.

Measures

Big Five Inventory 10 (BFI -10): The BFI-10 developed by Rammstedt and John (2007) is a ten items scale that assesses the big five personality traits: Openness to experience, Conscientiousness, agreeableness, extraversion and neuroticism. It's a short-scale version of BFI (Big Five Inventory). It allows assessing the big five

factors by two items each within a minute or less. The items are rated on a five-point Likert scale named as disagree strongly, disagree a little, neither agree nor disagree, agree a little and agree strongly. Rammstedt and John (2007) demonstrated test-retest correlations between $r=.65$ (Openness), $r =.49$ (Neuroticism & $r=.79$ (Extraversion) over a period of 6 to 8 weeks and validity of .64.

Adult Suicide Ideation Questionnaire: ASIQ is 25 items self-report measure developed by William (1987) ASIQ helps find individuals having suicidal thoughts in the past month. It offers a seven-point rating scale, with the options being practically daily, a few times per week, about once a week, a few times per month, or about once a month, I've thought about this previously but not recently, and I've never thought about this. It also contains six critical items (CI), out of which if two are 5 or greater then it's considered serious regardless of the total scoring. ASIQ's internal consistency coefficient range from .96 to .97 and the retest coefficient range from 0.85 to .95

Psychological Well-being Scale by Ryff (18 items): The PWS-18 is an 18 items short version scale of 42 items PWS developed by Ryff and Keyes (1995). On six subscales, including environmental mastery, autonomy, personal growth, life purpose, positive relationships with others, and self-acceptance, it assesses the psychological well-being of adults. It's rated on a seven-point scale named as strongly disagree, somewhat agree, a little agree, neither agree nor disagree, a little disagree, somewhat disagree, and strongly disagree. It is highly valid test with test retest coefficient .82.

Procedure

The design for data collection was a hybrid of two modalities for the easier availability of the sample. The data was collected in two modes - Online and Offline. The online mode was done with Google Forms through modalities such as What Sapp, Instagram, and Telegram. The offline mode was taken through hard copies of the standardized questionnaires handed out to the participants. It took over 40 days for receiving 200 responses from varied demographics.

Statistical Analysis

In direction to test the hypotheses of the study, data analysis was carried out by using SPSS version 16. To see whether the variable personality traits have any relationship with psychological well-being and/or suicidal ideation, we will be using correlational analysis.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of Suicide Ideation, Dimensions of Psychological Well-being and Dimensions of Personality

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Suicide ideation	25.21	22.044	200
Open	6.50	1.604	200
Conscientiousness	6.40	1.710	200
Extroversion	6.03	1.949	200
Agreeableness	7.14	1.821	200
Neuroticism	6.18	1.920	200
self-accept	14.28	3.594	200
Autonomy	11.76	3.028	200
Envir. mastery	13.82	2.894	200
Purpose in life	14.71	3.314	200
Positive relation	13.08	3.661	200
Personal growth	15.91	3.512	200

Table 2*Correlation between Personality Traits, Psychological Well-being and Suicide Ideation*

Sr.no	Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	Openness	1	.116	.085	.246**	.029	.081	-.214**	.072	.201**	-.035	.256**	-.107
2	Conscientiousness		1	.069	.222**	-.163*	.211**	.143*	.220**	.069	.089	.063	-.029
3	Extrovert			1	-.021	-.412**	.269**	.155*	.246**	.056	.217**	.199**	-.278**
4	Agreeable				1	.076	-.071	-.242**	.181*	.093	.053	.172*	-.101
5	Neuroticism					1	-.310**	-.158*	-.340**	-.093	-.186**	-.193**	.356**
6	Self-acceptance						1	.193**	.305**	-.096	.199**	.177*	-.164*
7	Autonomy							1	.004	.064	.174*	.095	-.056
8	Envir. Mastery								1	-.026	.056	.224**	-.145*
9	Purpose in life									1	.136	.371**	-.216**
10	Positive relation										1	.251**	-.241**
11	Personal growth											1	-.224**
12	Suicide ideation												1

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Discussion

Our research aimed to assess the impact of traits of personality on psychological well-being and suicidal ideation among adults in Haryana 18-25 years. Young adults have a lot to deal with - new roles, responsibilities and complex social interactions - which influences their success-making and goal attainment. Very often, their psychological well-being is impacted by their personality traits due to which they are unable to lead a balanced and successful life in their adulthood.

In Table 1, the mean and standard deviation of suicide ideation was found to be 25.21 and 22.04, and Personality traits with five dimensions have a mean score in the range of 6-7. In Psychological well-being, it was 13.92 and 3.33 and the six dimensions have a mean score in the range of 11-16. We hypothesized that there would be no relationship between personality traits, psychological well-being and suicide ideation. Through the correlational analysis, we could say that both null hypotheses were rejected with significant relationships between personality traits, psychological well-being and suicide ideation.

The Pearson correlation coefficient was identified to assess the linear relationship between personality traits, psychological well-being and suicide ideation. The Table-2 displays the correlation coefficients between these twelve variables: Openness, Conscientiousness, Extrovert, Agreeableness, Neuroticism, Self-acceptance, Autonomy, Envir. Mastery, Purpose in life, Positive relation, Personal growth, Suicide ideation, and these correlation coefficients represent the strength and direction of the relationships between each pair of variables. It shows that openness is weak negatively correlated with Autonomy (-.214**) and weak positively correlated with Purpose in life (.201**) and Personal growth (.256**). Conscientiousness is positively weak correlated with Self-acceptance (.211**) and Environmental Mastery (.220**). Extrovert is positively correlated with Self-acceptance (.269**), Envir. Mastery (.246**) and Positive relation (.217**) and negatively correlated with Suicide ideation (-.278**). Agreeableness is negatively correlated with Autonomy (-.242**). Neuroticism is negatively correlated with Self-acceptance (-.310**), Environmental Mastery (-.340**), personal growth (-.193**) and positively correlated with Suicide ideation (.356**).

On the basis of findings, it is concluded that openness is negatively

correlated with suicide ideation and positively correlated with psychological well-being (Kokko, Tolvanen, & Pulkkinen, 2013). Conscientiousness is positively correlated with Psychological well-being (Grant, Langan-Fox, & Anglim, 2009). Extrovert is also positively correlated with Psychological Well-being and negatively correlated with Suicidal Ideation (Kokko, Tolvanen, & Pulkkinen, 2013). Agreeableness is negatively correlated with Suicide ideation (DeShong, Tucker, O'Keefe, Mullins-Sweatt, & Wingate, 2015). Neuroticism is negatively correlated with Psychological well-being and positively correlated with Suicide ideation (Rappaport, Flint, & Kendler, 2017). These findings provide valuable insights into the interrelationships between different factors and can be useful for understanding the dynamics and impact of these variables in the given context.

Limitations and Future Implications of Study

Although data was gathered equally from both genders in different cities and villages of Haryana the sample used for the study is smaller ($N=200$). All the other states of India are also excluded from the study. Similar, studies should be carried out across India using a more diverse population in various environments with various cultures, settings, and contexts. There have only been a few studies conducted in India, particularly in the Haryana state that examines the relationship between the big five personality traits and psychological well-being. The study can help identify which personality traits contribute more to Psychological Well-being and suicidal ideation. Thus help can be provided to those individuals who are having suicidal thoughts and by providing therapeutic help to them they can be saved from committing suicide shortly.

References

- Costa, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (1992). The five-factor model of personality and its relevance to personality disorders. *Journal of Personality Disorders*, 6(4), 343-359. <https://doi.org/10.1521/pedi.1992.6.4.343>
- Daniel, S. S., & Goldston, D. B. (2012). Hopelessness and lack of connectedness to others as risk factors for suicidal behavior across the lifespan: Implications for cognitive-behavioral treatment. *Cognitive and Behavioral Practice*, 19(2), 288-300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpra.2011.05.003>
- DeShong, H. L., Tucker, R. P., O'Keefe, V. M., Mullins-Sweatt, S. N., & Wingate, L. R. (2015). Five factor model traits as a predictor of suicide ideation and interpersonal suicide risk in a college sample. *Psychiatry Research*, 226(1), 217-223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2015.01.002>

- Devi, N.P., & Raju, M.V.R. (2018). *Suicidal ideation among teenagers a study on higher secondary students in north coastal districts of Andhra Pradesh*. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/381338>
- Easterlin, R. A. (2006). Life cycle happiness and its sources: Intersections of psychology, economics, and demography. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 27(4), 463-482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2006.05.002>
- Gili-Planas, M., Roca-Bennasar, M., Ferrer-Perez, V., & Bernardo-Arroyo, M. (2001). Suicidal ideation, psychiatric disorder, and medical illness in a community epidemiological study. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 31(2), 207-213. <https://doi.org/10.1521/suli.31.2.207.21508>
- Grant, S., Langan-Fox, J., & Anglim, J. (2009). The big five traits as predictors of subjective and psychological well-being. *Psychological Reports*, 105(1), 205-231. <https://doi.org/10.2466/PRO.105.1.205-231>
- Hall, C., Lindsey, C., & Campbell, J. (1998). *Theories of personality* (Fourth edition). John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York.
- Hicks, R. E., & Mehta, Y. P. (2018). The big five, type A personality, and psychological well-being. *International Journal of Psychological Studies*, 10(1), 49. doi: 10.5539/ijps.v10n1p49 <https://dictionary.apa.org/adulthood>
- Huang, H. L., Peng, W. D., Lin, Y. C., Lee, C. H., Hu, C. Y., Huang, S. T. (2017). Gender-specific factors associated with the suicidal ideation of children in Taiwan: A large-scale cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Psychology*, 54(1), 53-60. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12438>
- Inder, K., Handley, T., Johnston, A., Weaver, N., Coleman, C., Lewin, T., Slade, T., & Kelly, B. (2014). Determinants of suicidal ideation and suicide attempts: Parallel cross-sectional analyses examining geographical location. *BMC Psychiatry*, 14, 1-20. Doi: 10.1186/1471-244X-14-208
- Kokko, K., Tolvanen, A., & Pulkkinen, L. (2013). Associations between personality traits and psychological well-being across time in middle adulthood. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 47(6), 748-756. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2013.07.002>
- Lasgaard, M., Goossens, L., & Elklit, A. (2011). Loneliness, depressive symptomatology, and suicide ideation in adolescence: Cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, 39, 137-150. Doi: 10.1007/s10802-010-9442-x
- Liu, R.T., Lawrence, H.R., Burke, T.A., Sanzari, C.M., Levin, R.Y., Maitlin, C., Paszek, C., & Zhu, X. (2021). Passive and active suicidal ideation among left-behind children in rural China: An evaluation of intrapersonal and interpersonal vulnerability and resilience. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 51(6), 1213-1223. Doi: 10.1111/sltb.12802.
- Nock, M. K., Borges, G., Bromet, E. J., Alonso, J., Angermeyer, M., Beautrais, A., Bruffaerts, R., Chiu, W. T., de Girolamo, G., Gluzman, S., de Graaf, R., Gureje, O., Haro, J. M., Huang, Y., Karam, E., Kessler, R. C., Lepine, J. P., Levinson, D., Medina-Mora, M. E., & Williams, D. (2008). Cross-national prevalence and risk factors for suicidal ideation, plans and attempts. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 192(2), 98-105. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.107.040113>
- O'Carroll, P., Berman, A., Maris, R., Moscicki, E., Tanney, B., & Silverman, M. (1996). Beyond the tower of babel: A nomenclature for suicidology. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 26, 237-252. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1943-278X.1996.tb00609.x>
- Oliver, P. H., Guerin, D. W., & Coffman, J. K. (2009). Big five parental personality traits, parenting behaviors, and adolescent behavior problems: A mediation model. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 47(6), 631-636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2009.05.026>
- Palmer, Jr. C. J. (2004). Suicide attempt history, self-esteem, and suicide risk in a sample of 116 depressed voluntary inpatients. *Psychological Reports*, 95(3_suppl), 1092-1094. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.95.3f.1092-1094>
- Passive Suicidal Ideation: What it is and What You Can Do. <https://www.psycom.net/depression/passive-suicidal-ideation>
- Posner, K., Brodsky, B., Yershova, K., Buchanan, J., & Mann, J. (2014). The classification of suicidal behavior. In M. K. Nock (Ed.), *The Oxford handbook of suicide and self-injury* (pp. 7-22). Oxford University Press.
- Rappaport, L. M., Flint, J., & Kendler, K. S. (2017). Clarifying the role of neuroticism in suicidal ideation and suicide attempt among women with major depressive disorder. *Psychological Medicine*, 47(13), 2334-2344. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S003329171700085X>
- Roberts, B. W., Walton, K. E., & Viechtbauer, W. (2006). *Personality traits change in adulthood: Reply to Costa and McCrae (2006)*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.132.1.29>
- Ryff, C. D. (1989). Happiness is everything, or is it? Explorations on the meaning of psychological well-being. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 57(6), 1069-1081. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.57.6.1069>
- Ryff, C. D. (1995). Psychological well-being in adult life. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 4(4), 99-104. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.ep10772395>
- Schultz, D., & Schultz, S. (2017). *Theories of personality* (Eleventh Edition). 20 Channel Center Street, Boston, MA 02210, USA.
- Steve Baumgardner, S., & Crothers, M. (2014). *Positive psychology* (First Edition). Pearson Education Limited, Edinburgh Gate, Harlow, Essex CM20 2JE.
- Upadhyay, B. K., & Singh, R. (2006). Suicide ideation and psychopathology among adolescents. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 2(3), 423-429.
- Voracek, M. (2013). Regional analysis of big five personality factors and suicide rates in Russia. *Sage Journals*. <https://doi.org/10.2466/09.12.PR0.113x13z4>
- Wellman, R. J., & Wellman, M. M. (1988). Correlates of suicidal ideation in a college population. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 23, 90-95.
- William, R. (1987). *Manual of adult suicidal ideation questionnaire*. Psychological Assessment Resource, Inc. Ziaaddini, H., Navadeh, S., & Saeedi, A. (2009). "Prevalence of suicide ideation", attempts and the associated factors among a sample of Iranian population in South part of the country: A population based study. *Iran Journal of Psychiatry*, 4(1), 92-96.
- World Health Organization (2014). Preventing suicide: A global imperative. *CMAJ: Canadian Medical Association Journal*, 143, 609-610.
- World Health Organization (2004). *Global burden of disease*. <http://www.who.int/healthinfo/global>